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IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES

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Abstract. This article examines the importance of effective management in ensuring the economic development of small industrial zones (SIZs). The study analyzes key areas such as SIZ infrastructure, improvement of the investment climate, digital transformation, and public-private partnership. In addition, practical recommendations are provided for improving management mechanisms based on international experience and the specific conditions of Uzbekistan. The article proposes management approaches aimed at increasing the economic efficiency of small industrial zones and promoting regional development.

Keywords: small industrial zones, investment climate improvement, infrastructure development, digital transformation, strategic planning, management mechanisms, economic efficiency, regional development, logistics, human capital development.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается значение эффективного управления в обеспечении экономического развития малых промышленных зон (МПЗ). В исследовании проанализированы ключевые направления развития МПЗ, включая совершенствование инфраструктуры, улучшение инвестиционного климата, цифровую трансформацию и развитие механизмов государственно-частного партнёрства. Кроме того, на основе международного опыта и с учётом особенностей Республики Узбекистан разработаны практические рекомендации по совершенствованию механизмов управления. В статье предложены подходы к управлению, направленные на повышение экономической эффективности малых промышленных зон и стимулирование регионального развития.

Ключевые слова: малые промышленные зоны, улучшение инвестиционного климата, развитие инфраструктуры, цифровая трансформация, стратегическое планирование, механизмы управления, экономическая эффективность, региональное развитие, логистика, развитие человеческого капитала.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, profound changes in the global economy and the rapid pace of technological development have necessitated a new approach to shaping industrial policy in many countries. In particular, to ensure sustainable economic growth and competitiveness, the establishment of regional industrial infrastructure, such as small industrial zones (SIZs), has been adopted as a key strategic tool in various countries.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issues of effective management of industrial zones and the enhancement of their competitiveness have been extensively studied by Michael Porter. The concept of clustering is substantiated in his seminal works *The Competitive Advantage of Nations* (1990) and *Clusters and the New Economics of Competition* (1998) [1]. According to Porter, the geographical concentration of enterprises within a particular area increases

production efficiency, stimulates innovation, and accelerates economic growth. This approach provides a theoretical foundation for the development of cooperative relationships in the management of small industrial zones.

The practical aspects of industrial zone management are comprehensively analyzed in the World Bank report *Special Economic Zones: An Operational Review of Their Impacts* (2017) [2]. The report demonstrates that the successful operation of industrial zones depends on effective management, well-developed infrastructure, a favorable investment climate, and strong institutional support.

The report *Industrial Parks and Economic Transformation* (2021), published by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), emphasizes the importance of introducing innovative approaches, digitalization, and environmental sustainability principles into the management of industrial zones. According to the findings of the report, modern management systems significantly improve the economic efficiency and long-term sustainability of industrial zones.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods, including systematic and comparative analysis, economic-statistical analysis, generalization, correlation and regression analysis, grouping techniques, economic modeling, and forecasting methods. These approaches enabled a comprehensive assessment of the factors influencing the performance of small industrial zones, the identification of existing challenges, and the development of scientifically grounded recommendations for improving their management efficiency.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Small industrial zones are specially designated areas aimed at centralizing industrial production, developing regional economies, creating new jobs, and supporting local businesses. They serve as an important platform for providing favorable infrastructure, services, investment opportunities, and an innovation-friendly environment for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

In developing countries such as Uzbekistan, the development of small industrial zones plays a significant role in strengthening regional economic stability and competitiveness. These zones provide an important foundation for the efficient use of local raw material resources, expansion of export potential, technological modernization, and implementation of innovations. At the same time, the management system of economic activities within these zones is a decisive factor in ensuring their successful operation and long-term sustainability [3].

In practice, the efficiency of managing small industrial zones is influenced by multiple factors, and several issues remain relevant in this area. Infrastructure in many zones requires further development; attracting investment can be challenging, and existing management mechanisms need to be further improved in line with modern requirements and international standards. Therefore, improving the economic efficiency of small industrial zones, introducing modern management approaches, and expanding innovative mechanisms have become urgent tasks.

The purpose of this research is to identify key directions for improving the management processes of small industrial zones and to develop effective governance mechanisms based on these findings. The study aims to analyze existing issues in managing the activities of small industrial zones, examine international best practices, and propose management models tailored to the specific conditions of Uzbekistan. In addition, the research considers digital transformation, public-private partnerships, investment climate improvement, and innovative approaches as essential factors in enhancing the efficiency of small industrial zone management.

Currently, the economic development of small industrial zones plays a vital role not only in diversifying regional industry but also in strengthening the global competitiveness of the national economy. Therefore, by improving their management systems, it is possible not only to increase production volumes but also to create new jobs and ensure socio-economic well-being in the regions. To achieve this, it is essential to implement scientifically grounded management approaches, establish effective institutions, and widely adopt innovative tools and modern technologies.

Based on the conducted analyses and practical observations, it has been identified that the effective management system of small industrial zones needs further improvement, which remains one of the key factors influencing their development. The following findings were revealed:

Infrastructure development. In a number of zones, electricity supply, transportation, and communication networks require further improvement.

Access to financial resources. Enterprises need broader access to preferential loans, subsidies, and investment attraction mechanisms.

Personnel qualification. The local labor force should be further prepared for modern technologies and contemporary management practices.

Innovation development. Many zones have significant potential to expand the adoption of digital technologies, automation, and innovative product development.

Unified management system. There is a need to develop a coordinated strategy for managing regional industrial zones within a unified framework.

Environmental requirements. Environmental protection measures should be strengthened and consistently implemented.

Small industrial zones constitute an essential part of the national economy. They play a significant role in developing local production, creating new jobs, and implementing innovative projects. At the same time, the effective management of small industrial zones is a decisive factor in ensuring their sustainable development. This article highlights the key directions for improving the management of small industrial zones and their importance [4].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, a comprehensive study and practical application of measures aimed at improving the effective management of small industrial zones can serve as a foundation for shaping new drivers of economic growth in Uzbekistan's regions, enhancing the quality and volume of industrial production, expanding export potential, and ensuring social stability. Therefore, this topic is of significant importance for the country's economic development, and it is essential to study it in depth and implement advanced management practices.

Small industrial zones play an important role in the sustainable development of the national economy. Their advancement contributes not only to the creation of new jobs, but also to the enhancement of local production capacity, the introduction of innovations, and the expansion of export potential. Therefore, ensuring the effective management of small industrial zones is a necessary condition for their stable and dynamic development.

Improving management processes largely depends on analyzing the internal and external environment of industrial zones, developing infrastructure, implementing modern technologies, and ensuring the efficient allocation of financial resources. Research and practical experience show that one of the most critical factors in the development of small industrial zones is the introduction of high-quality infrastructure and digitalized management systems. At the same time, expanding financial support mechanisms for enterprises operating within industrial zones, as well as improving systems for attracting loans and investment, contributes to increased economic efficiency.

The adoption of innovations and new technologies plays a key role in enhancing the competitiveness of small industrial zones. Therefore, it is essential to focus on creating innovative management systems, developing scientific and technical cooperation, and training qualified personnel. A skilled workforce and competent management staff are among the primary drivers of rapid and high-quality industrial zone development.

In the management of small industrial zones, the implementation of quality and performance monitoring systems is of great importance. These systems ensure continuous control over production processes, enabling the timely identification and resolution of issues. Such monitoring contributes to improving enterprise performance and enhancing competitiveness.

Moreover, taking into account environmental requirements and applying the principles of a green economy ensure the long-term and sustainable development of small industrial zones. Compliance with environmental protection regulations and legal standards not only guarantees ecological safety but also contributes to increasing the efficiency of production processes.

Fostering close cooperation among local authorities, businesses, and scientific and technical institutions helps strengthen the scientific and technical foundation of small industrial zones, facilitates the implementation of new projects, and promotes the expansion of innovative approaches. In addition, developing and applying effective marketing strategies enables small industrial zones to strengthen their position in the market and enhance their export potential.

Improving the legal and regulatory framework and optimizing the management system create a more favorable business environment within industrial zones and facilitate the effective governance of enterprises. Simplified procedures, faster permitting processes, and clear regulations help streamline operations and stimulate business activity in these zones.

In general, improving the effective management of small industrial zones requires an integrated approach that covers infrastructure development, innovation, financial support, workforce training, quality monitoring, environmental protection, cooperation, and legal aspects. The comprehensive implementation of these areas enhances the economic potential of small industrial zones, strengthens their role in the national economy, and ensures their sustainable development.

Therefore, both government bodies and business representatives should pay special attention to the above-mentioned improvement directions when developing and implementing strategies for the advancement of small industrial zones. This will significantly contribute not only to the development of industrial zones themselves, but also to the overall economic growth of the country.

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